

TIMOTEI CIPARIU' S GRAMMAR, A MODEL OF INTERCULTURALITY

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ABSTRACT

In this approach, as in our other articles, we return to the role played by a Romanian scholar from the 19th century in creating contact between Romanian culture and other European cultures. This time, the detailed plan is the linguistic one, by describing the first grammar of the Romanian language, of an academic type, written by Timotei Cipariu in the period 1869-1877.

KEY-WORDS: interculturality, academic grammar, language.

1. Timotei Cipariu, linguistic beginnings

At the time he wrote the *Gramateca limbei române* (1869-1877), Timotei Cipariu was not at his first attempt in this field. He had already published in 1854 the work *Elemente de limba română după dialecte și monumente vechi*, considered as the first historical grammar of our language, and four (until 1876 five) editions of a *Compendiu de gramateca limbei române*, published for the first time in 1855, with a more practical character (obvious not only in the selection of the material and in the predominance of the descriptive character, but also in the presence of a "reading" part, including pieces chosen from various dishes).

Gramateca has totals 854 pages (I 384, II 411 and the Supplement 59 pages) in 8°. It should be noted from the very beginning that such dimensions had not been reached by any previous work on Romanian grammar. Otherwise, even the later grammars did not come close to these dimensions, and the comparison with the newer grammars is less conclusive, since they differ greatly in structure from Cipariu's grammar, in which we find many elements different from what we call grammar today.

Cipariu's work closely followed the requirements of the competition programs of the Academic Society for the two volumes. Even leaving aside the Supplement in the analysis of the Grammar

proper, it is easy to see, from the simple enumeration of its main divisions, that the work includes chapters whose inclusion in the grammar seems strange to the modern reader and, therefore, it has been criticized in some analyses. It is not, of course, about phonetics or the formation of words, which until today we meet in many grammars in addition to their actual object, morphology and syntax, but about the chapters devoted to spelling and forms of diction, including tropes.

It must be pointed out, however, that the presence of an orthography chapter was in the tradition of Romanian grammarians starting from the first works of Dimitrie Eustatievici, Macarie and Samuil Micu, and was required by the competition programs of the Academic Society for both parts of grammar. As for the otherwise brief treatment of tropes (in connection with the so-called ornate syntax), it also has precedent in several older grammars, such as that of the same Dimitrie Eustatievici, Ienăchiță Văcărescu or Andreas Clemens.

2. Echoes of the era related to Cipariu's grammar

An element that was not taken into account in the various subsequent criticisms brought to Cipariu's Grammar is precisely the reference, on the one hand, to previous grammars, on the other hand to the requirements of the followed program. It is significant, in this respect, that Cipariu could be criticized for paying too little attention to syntax, limiting himself to the syntax of the parts of speech, the parts of the sentence and the topic, without noticing that syntax is precisely the part of grammar that he developed the most compared to the works up to that point. An injustice is done here to Cipariu, which can be said to have started even with the debates on his manuscript of syntax, appreciated by the Romanian Academic Society less favorably than the first one. The main contradiction seems to be between the appreciations on which the prize was based, respectively the rewarding of the work by the Academic Society, when at least the first part of Cipariu's Grammar was qualified as "a really serious, conscientious work full of profound erudition and vast knowledge on the subject, a work that would do honor to the best and most developed literatures in this part of philology and which any academy could crown with both hands"¹, and the

¹ *Analele Societății Academice Române*, tomul I, p. 161.

fact that later it could be considered a "failure"² or an "example of scientific error"³. In addition to this striking contradiction, there are others, as far as the concrete assessments of certain aspects are concerned.

The negative opinions cited above refer to the etymological, Latinizing orientation of Cipariu's Grammar. For the same reason, it was stated that "the work was outdated even at its appearance"⁴. Of course, a work with rebarbarative Latinizing spelling appeared in the middle of the battle between the phonetic current, with wide popular echoes, and the etymological current, was condemned to be ignored and indirectly perhaps contributed to the victory of the opposite direction.

It is understandable that at the respective historical moment the destruction of Latinism was more important than the recognition of the qualities of a certain Latinist work, but we can regret the fact that the underappreciation of the work in question was perpetuated in conditions where it no longer constituted a necessity, as well as the fact that this underappreciation is primarily due to a formal, presentational aspect, neglecting the content qualities of the Grammar.

Of course, the etymology of Cipariu's Grammar is not only limited to spelling (let's not forget that a chapter is dedicated to it, so, in addition to the general external appearance, it also constitutes a problem of content) and expression, but also manifests itself in the way of description, explanations and especially normative indications.

The cause of the underappreciation of Cipariu's Grammar is also not limited to the etymological orientation alone. I previously mentioned the fact that the work presents a mixture of history and dialectology, a conglomeration of old and dialectal forms put on the same level as those existing in current modern use or even preferred to them in paradigms. During the debates on the first part of Cipariu's Grammar, Heliade called it a "store of forms of the Romanian language" (recognizing the "scientific merit of the opus", which he considers "the work of a human life", he refuses the title of grammar and declares

² În *Cuvânt înainte*, semnat de D. Macrea, la *Gramatica limbii române*, apărută sub egida Academiei Române, vol. I, 1954, p. 15.

³ Iorgu Iordan, *Preocupări de limbă la Academia Română*, LR, XV, 1966, nr. 5, p. 765.

⁴ Mariana Costinescu, *Normele limbii literare în gramaticile românești*, Editura Didactică și Pedagogică, București, 1979, p.12.

himself in agreement with awarding the work as any other kind of study, but not as grammar)⁵.

3. Grammar of Timotei Cipariu, a model of interculturality

Cipariu does not neglect the modern aspect of the language, he even notes peculiarities that are rarely found in writing, such as the non-pronunciation of the definite articles *-l* and *-i* or the genitive-dative of *lui Maria* type, he discusses the difference in the use of the articulated forms of the genitive-dative singular feminine in *-ii* and in *-ei* according to the spoken or scholarly aspect of the language, he condemns the fact that "our newest writers" write *domnitorele* sau *autorele*, he remarks the development of the phenomenon of resuming the direct and indirect complement through unstressed forms of the personal pronoun etc. That is why, Mioara Avram believes, it is unfair to say about him that he "stopped ... at the language of the 16th century" (even if we exaggerate the place of the old forms in his grammar, we must note that they are also from the 17th and 18th centuries) and to attribute to him "willful ignorance of the living language of the people and the literature his contemporaries"⁶. The few examples given above are also welcome to concretely demonstrate that Cipariu recognized the linguistic evolution and did not neglect the use of speech.

For the other aspect, of the repetitions in the work, given their existence especially in volume II, in the sense of resuming some problems treated in volume I, it is probably possible to invoke a detail related to the time and manner of elaboration of the work: first of all, it should not be forgotten that the two volumes were written and published separately, at a distance of eight years from each other. Secondly, it seems that the first volume was worked on in a hurry according to the short deadline granted by the Academic Society, therefore, when presenting the manuscript, the author reserved the right to a revision before printing and it is likely that this is also why he felt the need to come back with various clarifications of pure morphology at the time of treating the syntax.

⁵ *Analele*, tomul I, p. 155, 165.

⁶ Mioara Avram, *Prima gramatică academică a limbii române*, în LR, XV, 1966, nr. 5, p. 494.

Conclusions

The value of a normative work from the 19th century should be judged from two points of view: on the one hand in relation to the moment in which it was written and published, and on the other in relation to the current state of our knowledge.

We will also add reporting to the grammars of other Romanian languages, the links that the first academic grammar of the Romanian language made on a linguistic and cultural level.

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